

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

ORGANIZATION OF WORK WITH INCLUSIVE STUDENTS IN THE COURSE «HISTORY OF WORLD LITERATURE»

Alimova N.

*Associate Professor of the Department of Russian Literary Studies
Faculty of Journalism and Uzbek Philology,
National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek
Uzbekistan, Tashkent*

Abstract

The article presents the specific features of organizing classes for visually impaired students studying in undergraduate academic groups. One of the approaches in organizing classes for inclusive students is the integration of independent and individualized learning. At the current stage of Uzbekistan's development, within classroom conditions, there is an opportunity to use special teaching aids and educational environments. The educational process for visually impaired students becomes possible and comfortable when certain organizational conditions are met.

Keywords: inclusive education, students with disabilities, technical teaching aids, vocational education, socialization, integration.

Introduction.

Over the past five years, the higher education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan has been implementing a concept for the development of inclusive education. Young people with physical disabilities have gained the opportunity to become highly qualified and competitive in the labor market. This has become possible due to state policies aimed at creating an accessible environment and ensuring the rights of youth with special educational needs.

Based on Presidential Decree No. 5270 of December 1, 2017, "On Measures to Radically Improve the System of State Support for Persons with Disabilities," the Law "On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities" was adopted. Chapter 6 – "Education, Vocational Training, Retraining and Professional Development of Persons with Disabilities," and Article 38 – "Right of Persons with Disabilities to Education," are devoted to the educational process of inclusive youth within the framework of current legislation. The state guarantees free general secondary, additional, specialized secondary, and vocational education. "Persons with disabilities have the right to education in educational institutions and throughout their lives for the fullest development of their abilities and participation in the life of society and the state. The state guarantees the development of inclusive education for persons with disabilities, and the creation of necessary conditions for access to education, vocational training, retraining, and advanced training." [1, c.16]

The process of inclusive education has fundamentally changed society's attitude toward this issue. In order to ensure comprehensive and harmonious development of students, foster social activity, cultivate interest in the educational process and academic disciplines, and involve students in research activities, university professors create the necessary conditions. Adapting to new circumstances, competencies are being developed: methodological literature, recommendations, and original techniques and methods for inclusive students.

Main Part. The ongoing process of improving the education system for inclusive students – through the development of the most suitable languages and teaching methods for each of them (multimedia tools, information and communication technologies) – has placed new demands on teachers. Unlike schoolchildren, university students already possess many technologies: Braille, alternative fonts, speech and oral communication methods. Therefore, the use of specific teaching methods, adapted curricula, and an individual approach to each student, as well as their socialization, becomes the teacher's priority.

In inclusive education, the system is not about adapting the student to education; rather, inclusion adapts the environment, methods, and programs. However, this is a mutual learning process. A teacher, maintaining close communicative contact, can ensure the student receives the full content of the course and its teaching methodology.

Lecture courses do not present significant difficulties. Visually impaired students listen and take notes (using Braille) like other students, except for visual content such as presentations. The lecturer's task is to enhance such content with vivid oral explanations to help create visual imagery for visually impaired students.

For the course "History of World Literature" (Education Program 60230100 – Philology and Language Teaching, Russian Language), the curriculum allocates 24 hours for lectures and 24 hours for seminars.

Lecture Topics Include:

- History of Ancient Literature
- Drama of Ancient Greece and Rome
- Comedy of Ancient Greece and Rome
- Medieval Literature. Heroic Epic
- Renaissance Literature
- Reformation in Germany. Renaissance in France
- Renaissance in Spain and England
- The 17th Century as a Special Historical and Cultural Epoch

- 17th-Century Literature in England and Germany
- Enlightenment in England
- Enlightenment in France
- Enlightenment in Germany

All course materials (lecture texts, presentations, literature, assignments) are uploaded on the Hhemis.nuu.uz platform. However, visually impaired students cannot fully access this content. Therefore, publicly available audio materials (educational films, audiobooks) were added. Lecture material does not pose difficulties, but seminars require special adaptation.

Seminars aim to consolidate theoretical knowledge and develop contextual analysis and interpretation skills using specific literary works.

Seminar Topics Include:

- Myth in Antiquity
- The Genre of Tragedy in Ancient Greek Literature (Aeschylus, Sophocles)
- The Medieval Heroic Epic “The Song of Roland”
- Dante’s “Divine Comedy”
- Medieval Chivalric Romance “Tristan and Isolde”
- Problems of Shakespeare’s “Hamlet”
- French Classical Tragedy (Corneille, Racine)
- Comedy of Classicism (Molière)
- English Enlightenment Novel (Defoe, Swift)
- Voltaire’s Philosophical Tale
- Drama of the Enlightenment
- Goethe’s “Faust”

72 hours are allocated for **independent work**: preparation for seminars (30 hours), reading and analysis (30 hours), and project preparation and defense (12 hours).

The main goal of independent work is to develop creativity and independent thinking. Forms of independent work include studying and analyzing academic literature (note-taking, summarizing), delivering presentations, and participating in «round-table» discussions. It is recommended to prepare project work on key issues of the course. This type of work suggests both individual work as well as the use of pedagogical technology methods such as cooperative learning. For better socialization of inclusive students, participation in collective projects is necessary, where students complete one of the aspects of the overall work.

Suggested topics include:

- The creative method of Aristophanes
- The epic poetry of Homer and its poetic features
- The Age of Pericles – characteristics
- Structure of the Roman theatre and traditions of Roman tragedy
- The poem “Beowulf” and its poetic features
- Questions of literature in Aristophanes’ comedy “The Frogs” and Horace’s poem “Ars Poetica” (“The Art of Poetry”)
- Artistic features of the poem “The Song of the Nibelungs”
- Genres of urban literature
- Poetic features of Giovanni Boccaccio’s story “Fiammetta”
- Conflict and its resolution in William Shakespeare’s comedy “Twelfth Night”

- The genre of the fable in 18th-century European literature
- Sentimentalism as a literary movement
- “Celestina”: the high and the low in human nature

The option for implementing an adapted educational program for a particular student with a disability or a student with special educational needs is determined by the educational institution in accordance with recommendations and special conditions created within the organization.

When preparing for seminar classes in the course, it is necessary to be familiar with the texts of literary works. The instructor should also become familiar with Braille books and audiobooks, and, if necessary, replace untranslated texts with other works by the same author being studied.

Braille books can be purchased from specialized stores (e.g., Tiflocenter “Vertical,” smartaids.ru) and marketplaces such as Ozon. Free Braille books are mainly available through specialized libraries for visually impaired people that offer classical literature and textbooks. They can be downloaded (usually in .brl format) from websites such as BARD (NLS) and read using Braille displays. To obtain books, it is necessary to register with a specialized library or use their online services, which provide literature free of charge.

In Uzbekistan, there is a network of specialized libraries for blind and visually impaired people that provide access to literature, including books printed in Braille (raised-dot format) as well as audiobooks. The main institution is the Republican Central Special Library for the Blind, which holds the primary collection of Braille and audio literature and is located in Tashkent.

Libraries for blind and visually impaired people in Uzbekistan are present in almost all regions: Andijan Regional Library for the Blind, Karakalpakstan Republican Library for the Blind, Bukhara Regional Library for the Blind, Jizzakh Regional Library for the Blind, Kashkadarya Regional Library for the Blind.

Regional branches also operate in other regions, providing access to specialized materials. Large libraries offer books in Uzbek and Russian languages.

Enthusiasts Mirali Giyosov and Abdulaziz Salimov created the first online library in Uzbekistan for people with visual disabilities. The idea came to them after using a Russian equivalent platform. The project was supported by the Youth Agency and the NGO Sharait Plus.

Conclusion. At the present stage, the educational process aims to develop critical thinking skills, the ability to apply acquired knowledge, and the capacity to independently find necessary information and learn through self-education. The model of New Uzbekistan has expanded opportunities for inclusive students to actively participate in this process.

- Measures are being introduced to improve the provision of tutors in higher education institutions and to expand the practice of educating inclusive youth in universities.

- Emphasis is placed on developing an inclusive culture and organizing training sessions and seminars.

• Inclusive education helps overcome stereotypes and contributes to the creation of a more tolerant society.

When teaching inclusive students, the specificity lies in adjusting academic workloads, applying special forms and methods of instruction, and using educational programs adapted when necessary for these students.

References

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 641 dated 15.10.2020. On the Rights of Persons with Disabilities.
2. Presidential Decree No. 5270 dated 01.12.2017. On Measures to Radically Improve the System of State Support for Persons with Disabilities.